

ОСОБЕННОСТИ СВЯЗНОЙ РЕЧИ СТАРШИХ ДОШКОЛЬНИКОВ С ОБЩИМ НЕДОРАЗВИТИЕМ РЕЧИ

FEATURES OF CONNECTED SPEECH OF SENIOR PRESCHOOL CHILDREN WITH GENERAL SPEECH UNDERDEVELOPMENT

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В данной статье рассматривается развитие связной речи у детей старшего дошкольного возраста, которые сталкиваются с проблемами общего недоразвития речи. Характеризуются особенности связной речи у данной категории детей. Представлены результаты анализа уровня развития связной речи у 10 детей старшего дошкольного возраста с общим недоразвитием и в сравнении с детьми, у которых речевое развитие нормальное. Полученные данные подчеркивают необходимость активной работы по развитию связной речи у детей с общим недоразвитием, что является ключевым моментом в их обучении и развитии.

This article examines the development of coherent speech in older preschool children who face problems of general speech underdevelopment. The features of coherent speech in this category of children are characterized. The results of the analysis of the level of development of coherent speech in 10 older preschool children with general underdevelopment and in comparison with children with normal speech development are presented. The data obtained emphasize the need for active work on the development of coherent speech in children with general underdevelopment, which is a key point in their learning and development.

Ключевые слова: *связная речь, дети старшего дошкольного возраста, дошкольники, исследование, общее недоразвитие речи, особенности связной речи дошкольников.*

Key words: *coherent speech, children of senior preschool age, preschoolers, research, general speech underdevelopment, features of coherent speech of preschoolers.*

Introduction.

The problem of speech development remains relevant in our society, since from early childhood children absorb and reproduce the speech of their environment. Teachers (A.M. Leushina, E.I. Tikheyeva, K.D. Ushinsky, etc.), psychologists (A.A. Leontyev, L.S. Vygotsky, S.L. Rubinshtein) studied coherent speech in various aspects and etc.). Having developed coherent speech, a child is able to competently express his thoughts, answer questions, retell and compose stories, as well as interact with the world around him [9].

The child cannot use inflections, he cannot use prepositions, he grossly distorts the syllable structure and reduces complex words to one or two syllables. Phonemic hearing is impaired, many groups of sounds are impaired, and articulation is unclear and unstable [14].

Active and passive dictionaries have their own characteristics. Children have an understanding of words and therefore the passive vocabulary is relatively formed, but this does not apply to the active one, so there is a discrepancy in their volume. Children have difficulty translating words

from a passive vocabulary into an active one and putting it into practice in expressive speech. A manifestation of the poverty of the active vocabulary is that children pronounce many words inaccurately and have difficulty learning words that have a generalized meaning [8].

The great teacher V.P. Glukhov noted that coherent speech is not just a sequence of mental processes transformed into words and phrases, but is made up of all the linguistic achievements of children by a certain age. For children with general speech underdevelopment, expressing thoughts coherently is a difficult task that requires special attention and support [3].

General underdevelopment of speech varies from a complete lack of means of communication to the presence of extensive, but insufficiently literate and clear speech [2].

Children with general speech underdevelopment often have a limited vocabulary, which leads to repeated repetition of the same words with different meanings, making their statements monotonous and poor in expression. Preschoolers with such problems have difficulty forming coherent and coherent statements, which makes it difficult for them to fully express their thoughts and ideas [1; 14].

Children encounter difficulties in composing stories about their toys, fairy-tale characters or objects in accordance with a given plan. Often preschoolers limit themselves to a simple listing of objects and their components [2; 3].

In the process of retelling the text, preschoolers often lose the main meaning and miss key points, which leads to breaks in the plot. They get stuck on little things, breaking the logical sequence and repeating the same thing. Difficulties arise when trying to construct a complete story from a picture or series of pictures, which makes it difficult for them to express their thoughts and ideas in a coherent way [5; 13].

When analyzing the problem of the formation of coherent speech in preschool children with general speech underdevelopment, researchers such as: G.V. Chirkina, T.B. Filicheva and T.V. Tumanova The following components are considered as the main criteria for the formation of coherent speech [12]:

1. Level of proficiency in grammatical structures,
2. The ability to independently form words;
3. State of active and passive vocabulary;
4. The state of formation of the sound-syllable structure of a word.

The level of proficiency in grammatical structures in children with general speech underdevelopment is one of the main disorders. They have unformed prepositional-case constructions in phrasal and connected speech, as well as difficulties in using cases and prepositions. Difficulties arise when forming verbal phrases with nouns and prepositions.

Incorrect use of endings of nouns, adjectives and pronouns is observed; incorrect use and confusion of case endings of cardinal numerals; violations in the use of personal endings of verbs and endings of verbs in the past tense [6].

Children with general speech underdevelopment have limited lexical resources, which leads to stereotypicality and poverty in their statements. Difficulties arise with the logical sequence of thoughts and the formation of high-quality coherent speech. Children face the challenge of learning new words and expressions, which complicates the development of their vocabulary and leads to problems in its use [6, 11].

And as a result, all of the above components directly affect coherent speech and require pedagogical influence [10].

Purpose of the study: study of development coherent speech in children of senior preschool age with general speech underdevelopment and determining the level of development of coherent speech in this group of children.

Research methodology and organization.

We conducted a study in which 10 children of senior preschool age with gen-

eral underdevelopment of speech. Of these, 1 child had general speech underdevelopment II level, in 8 children - general speech underdevelopment III level and 1 a child with a conclusion – general speech underdevelopment of level IV.

The survey included about includes tasks proposed to identify the level of development and formation of coherent speech. The experiment was carried out using diagnostic tasks proposed by V.P. Glukhov [4].

We also used several series of tasks when studying children's coherent speech, which included:

- The first task is a retelling of the text (a familiar fairy tale);
- Second task – compiling a story – description;
- The third task is to compose a story based on a picture or a series of plot pictures;
- Fourth task – leave a story based on personal experience.

After When children complete tasks, we determine the levels of development of compilation: retelling, story based on a series of plot pictures, story – description and story based on personal experience.

For the retelling, we have identified the following criteria and indicators for assessing the level of formation:

4 points – children's texts are structured; detailed descriptions of events; coherence of thoughts

3-2 points – admit the absence of a detailed description of events

1-0 points – retelling a text for children consists of listing actions

For When compiling a story – description, we identified the following criteria and indicators for assessing the level of formation:

4 points – characterize the main features of the object

3-2 points – admit the absence of detailed characteristics of the characters

1-0 points – retelling a text for children consists of listing actions

For When composing a story based on a picture or a series of plot pictures, we highlight the following criteria and indicators for assessing the level of formation:

4 points – children's story is structured; detailed descriptions of events

3-2 points – admit the absence of a detailed description of events

1-0 points – retelling for children consists of listing actions

For Since leaving the story based on personal experience, we have identified the following criteria and indicators for assessing the level of formation:

4 points – children's story is structured; has a clear sequence and logic

3-2 points – admit the absence of a detailed description of events

1-0 points – the coherence of the presentation of thoughts is disrupted; make mistakes in constructing sentences

Research results and their rationale.

Based on the results of the experiment, it was found that the overall level of development of coherent speech in older preschoolers with general speech underdevelopment is distributed as follows: 10% of children have a high level of development, 30% have an average level, and 60% of children have a low level.

Analysis of the data showed that children with general speech underdevelopment differ significantly from their peers with normal development. Their proficiency in phrasal speech is low, which limits their communication capabilities

Children with general speech underdevelopment often exhibit a deficit in the structure of the meaning of a statement, constant repeated repetition of the same elements, as well as violations of the logical and semantic connection between fragments of text. Children often resort to using cues and gestures to point to the desired picture or detail. Complex and difficult to pronounce words in

the text cause them additional uncertainty, tension and confusion.

Pic. 1. General level of development of coherent speech in older preschoolers with general speech underdevelopment (%)

Most children observed a discrepancy between the semantic content of the story and the images in the pictures. The accuracy and completeness of the main characteristics of the object suffers, and a violation of the logical connection between the episodes in the pictures is revealed. Children have difficulty describing the details and features of an object.

Conclusions.

In our research, we found that children have difficulty mastering basic aspects of coherent language, such as telling a story using a series of pictures, telling a story based on personal experience, and retelling. The results obtained emphasize the importance of the continuous development of coherent speech skills in children throughout the entire process of correctional education and indicate the need for targeted correctional work.

The study of theoretical sources revealed that in order to form coherent speech in preschool children, it is necessary to have semantic content in statements, which arises only when the appropriate words are used and the rules of grammar are observed.

Characteristics of coherent speech in older preschoolers with general speech underdevelopment include a limited vocabulary, retelling with adult support, difficulties in planning utterances, logical sequencing, missing important events and getting stuck on details, lack of interest in works and independent problem solving, use of simple sentences and insufficient proficiency syntactic and grammatical structure of speech. These features emphasize the importance of studying the development of coherent speech in older preschool children with general speech underdevelopment.

Underdevelopment of coherent speech in preschool children with general speech underdevelopment negatively affects the development of their speech and cognitive abilities, making learning difficult. Solving this problem requires the intervention of specialists in correctional work with speech disorders and emphasizes the importance of speech development in older preschoolers with such difficulties.

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